

Numerical Modelling of Unstable Mode I Transverse Intralaminar Crack Propagation Using the Size Effect Law

L.F. Varandas, D. Dalli, G. Catalanotti, and B.G. Falzon

Advanced Composites Research Group (ACRG), School of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Queen's University Belfast, Belfast BT9 5AH, UK

1. Introduction

The use of composite materials in the automotive and aerospace sectors has necessitated the need to model and evaluate their mechanical performance under different loading scenarios.

The increased use of simulation at all stages of the development cycle (Figure 1) provides an opportunity to meet certain industrial shortcomings. To analyse the mechanical performance of the material, a numerical mesoscale framework is usually built. However, in most of the intralaminar damage models, the softening law associated with each failure mode is defined by the related **crack resistance curve (R-curve)**, which usually has to be determined experimentally.

Computational micromechanics can be an ideal tool to virtually analyse the effect of certain geometric and material variabilities, which are usually impossible to assess at lower resolution scales. Therefore, the **main objectives** of this work are to:

- Provide a 3D micromechanical tool to better understand the mechanisms behind intralaminar crack propagation.
- Highlight the advantages of the size effect method, originally proposed by Bažant [1], in a modelling perspective.

Fig. 1 – Experimental and numerical simulation of a QS crush of an UD composite tube [2].

2. Methodology

2.1 FE discretisation and Boundary Conditions

The computational framework is composed of Single Edge Notch Tension (SENT) virtual specimens, having a detailed micromechanical region, each composed of ten plies, with different random fibre distributions [3], while maintaining a constant fibre volume fraction. The reinforcements are embedded in an epoxy matrix. The micromechanical region is connected to the rest of the specimen through *Tie Constraints*.

Fig. 2 – Representation of the SENT models submitted to the appropriate BCs.

2.2 Material models

- Reinforcements – AS4 fibres. Transversely isotropic linear-elastic behaviour.
- Matrix – Elasto-plastic material damage model originally proposed by Melro et al. [4]. Fracture toughness characterised experimentally using the size effect method.
- Homogenised regions – Properties obtained using computational homogenisation. Transversely isotropic linear-elastic behaviour.

2.3 Determination of the correction factor

An analytical model is used to obtain the mode I transverse intralaminar *R*-curve, using the numerical peak loads obtained for different sizes of virtual specimens. This model requires the determination of a correction factor, κ , which is determined using the Virtual Crack Closure Technique (VCCT). A polynomial fit was obtained for this correction factor:

$$\kappa = \sqrt{\tan \frac{\pi \alpha}{2} \sum_i K_i \alpha^{i-1}}$$

where K_i is a matrix of indices for a 4th order fitting function for κ in terms of α [5].

Fig. 3 – Driving force curves for different scaled SENT models, and R-curve

Fig. 3 – VCCT model (left); κ vs α curve (right).

3. Results

3.1 Experimental Work

Fig. 5 – Experimental setup (top); fractured DENT specimens (bottom).

$h_c \approx 0$
Inserted by using the tapping method

The mode I *R*-curve of the epoxy is determined using the size effect law, by testing neat resin coupons of different sizes (Figure 5). The cracks were inserted making use of tapping method, in order not to overestimate the calculation of the fracture toughness. The steady-state value of the fracture toughness, and corresponding length of the fully developed Fracture Process Zone (FPZ) were approximately, $R_{ss} = 0.101$ kJ/m² and $l_{fpz} = 0.112$ mm, respectively.

Fig. 6 – Experimental mode I *R*-curve of the epoxy.

3.2 Numerical Results

The peak load increases with specimen size. However, this increase is not linearly proportional, indicating a size effect. Damage, even after unstable fracture, is shown to be contained within close proximity of the developed crack.

Fig. 7 – Contour plot of the matrix damage variable.

Fig. 8 – Peak loads obtained numerically (left); size effect law and corresponding bi-logarithmic fit [1] (right).

The driving force curves, $G_I(\Delta a)$, derived for different virtual specimen sizes (in blue), including those that were simulated using the computational framework (in red), were used to obtain the mode I transverse *R*-curve of the material (in black). The fully developed length of the FPZ, and the steady-state value of the fracture toughness, are respectively determined to be $l_{fpz} = 0.173$ mm and $R_{ss} = 207$ J/m², respectively.

Fig. 9 – Numerical prediction of the transverse mode I intralaminar *R*-curve.

References

- [1] - Bažant and Planas (1998). *CRC Press LCC*. [2] - Chiu et al. (2015). *Comp. Struc.* 131, 215-228. [3] - Varandas et al. (2017). *Comp. Struc.* 182, 326-334. [4] - Melro et al. (2013). *Int. J. of Sol. and Struc.* 50, 1897-1905. [5] - Catalanotti et al. (2014). *Eng. Frac. Mech.* 118, 49-65.

4. Conclusions and Future Work

- Various sizes of virtual SENT specimen, having a detailed micromechanical region, were generated and simulated, to numerically predict their respective peak loads. Using an analytical method and the size effect law [1], these peak loads were subsequently used to determine the transverse mode I *R*-curve of the material.
- Future developments of this framework will include the addition of interface regions, studying the sensitivity of the peak load to the pre-crack tip radius, and the sensitivity of the cell size and fibre volume fraction on the numerical predictions of the fracture toughness of the material.

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Contact the presenter

Luís Filipe Varandas
L.Varandas@qub.ac.uk

+44 (0)7546 781 719